

CONTROLLED INFLUENCE OF COMPONENT PROPERTIES USING HYBRID TECHNIQUES BY COMBINING DIFFERENT LIGHTWEIGHT STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Hybrid structures can be produced by combining two or more material partners with different mechanical properties with the aim to increase the properties of the resulting component such as stress-strain behaviour or impact resistance. Thus, the resulting part can consist of as an example a metal-metal, metal-plastic, or plastic-plastic combination. The latter is the focus of this work. Thermoplastic (TP) matrix systems are characterised by recyclability and weldability and are therefore ideal for the build-up of hybrid structures based on polymer-polymer materials. Combined with the outstanding properties (Young's modulus, tensile strength) of the reinforcing fibres, fibre-reinforced polymer composites are suitable for the production of hybrid structures. The resulting parts can be used primarily for structural components in the automotive sector where increased mechanical properties combined with lightweight are desired.

Compression moulding compounds based on glass fibre reinforced polypropylene (PP) combined with local reinforcing textile inserts are commonly used in the automotive industry to build-up hybrid components.

A new approach to produce the hybrid structures and to obtain the desired mechanical properties is the combination of a semi-finished part with comparative low mechanical properties as base material, such as compression moulding compounds and continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic sheets (organic sheets), with the thermoplastic in-situ tape placement technology to apply the local unidirectional reinforcement. The thermoplastic tape placement process is suitable for precise lay-up of unidirectional fibre reinforced tapes based on thermoplastic matrices without any additional post-consolidation steps [1]. The presented work follows

this approach and points out improvements compared to traditionally press processes.

2 Experimental

Based on the interest of the automotive industry to produce cars with lightweight properties and to integrate PP-GF and PA6-GF these two types of organic sheets were chosen as base material for this study. Organic sheets type TEPEX dynalite® 104-RG600(4) (PP) with a fibre volume content of 45 % and TEPEX dynalite® 102-RG600(4) (PA6) with a fibre volume content of 47 % supplied from Bond Laminates were used as base material. Unidirectional tapes from Ticona type CELSTRAN CFR-TP PP-GF, CELSTRAN CFR-TP PA6-GF with a width of 12 mm as well as Plytron PP-GF Tapes from ACM were used as local reinforcements. The specimens were produced by use of a 7 axis robotic thermoplastic tape placement system. As a heat source a hot gas torch with a mixture of H₂, O₂ and air was used to heat up the incoming tapes and the substrate. The incoming tapes were compacted at the nip point by a tempered compaction roller ($T_{\text{Roller}} = 55 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) with a compaction force of 4.5 bar (Fig.1). As process velocity 6 m/min was chosen.

To get a measure of the quality of the interlaminar bonding strength between the two material partners double ply wedge peel tests have been carried out [2]. By the wedge peel test it is also possible to get information of the correlation between interface bonding and process parameters for thermoplastic tape placement. For this purpose organic sheets (PP-GF) were locally reinforced under variation of gas volume and number of layers and afterwards cut into stripes (width = 15 mm, length = 300 mm).

Fixed by clamping device the specimens were pulled over a steel blade with constant velocity ($v_{\text{Peel}} = 20 \text{ mm/min}$). The resulting peel force was

measured by a 50 N load cell and digitalised by a software based measurement system.

Bending as well as tensile tests were carried out to determine the mechanical improvements of the reinforced structure according to the gas volume and the number of reinforcing layers. For the determination of tensile properties a Zwick universal testing machine 1485 with a maximum load of 250 kN and hydraulic clamping device was used. The tests were performed according to DIN EN ISO 527-4. The determination of flexural properties of the hybrid specimens was done with a Zwick universal testing machine 1475 according to DIN EN ISO 14125.

For examination if a combination of organic sheets with matrix inhomogeneous reinforcements is suitable to increase the mechanical properties, the apparent interlaminar shear strength was determined according to DIN EN 2563 on a Zwick universal testing machine 1475. Therefore organic sheets were locally reinforced by use of thermoplastic in-situ tape placement process with PA6-GF tapes as well as with PP-GF tapes. The apparent interlaminar shear strength is calculated by equation (1), where P_R is the maximum load at first failure, b the width of specimen, h the thickness of specimen.

$$\tau = \frac{3 P_R}{4bh} [MPa] \quad (1)$$

All specimens have been examined if the failure behaviour occurs in the joining zone between organic sheet and unidirectional reinforcement (Fig.2). Only the specimens with the mentioned failure behaviour were used for calculation of the apparent interlaminar shear strength.

For comparison of the two chosen manufacturing methods of the hybrid structure (thermoplastic tape placement and compression moulding) the impact behaviour was investigated according to DIN EN ISO 6603-2 on a drop weight impact device from CEAST. As penetration point the cross section was chosen. A round body with a diameter of 20 mm was chosen as impactor. The geometry of the specimens was two-ply crossed locally reinforced rectangular organic sheets with a thickness of 2 mm and a lateral length of 100 mm. On the one hand the local reinforcement (PP-GF Plytron) was applied to the organic sheet by thermoplastic in-situ tape placement process. On the other hand the reinforcement was prefixed by use of temperature resistant adhesive tape on the organic sheet and

joined afterwards by use of a hydraulic press from SATIM S.A.

The press was heated up to 270 °C and the TEPEX dynalite® 102-RG600(4) organic sheets with local reinforcements were inserted. After 5 seconds holding time at temperature and under pressure of 15 bar the specimen was cooled down to 80 °C while maintaining the pressure. The cooling phase was carried out for 1 hour. Afterwards the specimens were cut into described geometry.

The TEPEX dynalite® 104-RG600(4) organic sheets with local reinforcements were pressed at a temperature of 225 °C (cooling time = 1 hour, pressure = 15 bar).

In Table 1 a summary of all used materials as well as the produced specimens can be found.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Wedge peel tests

The specimens produced at 4 NI/min gas volume show an average peel force behaviour ($F_{max} = 9.29$ N, $\sigma_x = 2.81$). In contrast, the samples produced with higher gas volume ($\dot{V} = n[Nl/min]$, $n = \{6,8,10\}$) are characterised by excellent bonding strength. All tests exceeded the maximum capacity of the load cell and had to be aborted. Fig.3 shows for example the averaged peel force values for 4 NI/min and 6 NI/min gas volume. The significantly lower values for the samples which were produced with 4 NI/min gas volume can be explained that hereby not enough thermal energy was discharged to reach a complete and sufficient melting of the matrix from tape and substrate.

3.2 Tensile properties

According to the rule of mixtures the expected tensile strength of the specimens can be calculated as shown in equation (2), where σ_1 and σ_2 are the tensile strengths of the organic sheet and the unidirectional reinforcement as given by the manufactures. t_1 and t_2 are thickness values for the material partners.

$$\sigma_{th} = \frac{\sigma_1 t_1 + \sigma_2 t_2}{t_1 + t_2} \quad (2)$$

The stress behaviour of the tensile samples with 1 and 2 layers is characterised by a higher level of maximum stress comparable to the one predicted by equation (2) (Fig.4). On the other hand the

specimens with 3 and 4 layers of reinforcement show tensile values significantly lower than the theoretical ones. This can be explained by the fact that specimens with a higher amount of reinforcing layers were exposed locally to multiple thermal energy treatments and thus multiple heat-up phases. This can be traced back to the fact that from a certain number of layers the introduced heat cannot be detracted in a sufficient way without additional consolidation passes and thus deconsolidation of the laminate can occur. Khan has investigated similar phenomena for the in-situ consolidation of CF/PEEK [1].

Thus, it could be pointed out that a locally applied reinforcement shows a significant improvement of the tensile properties of the resulting hybrid structure if the implicated heat can be conducted in a sufficient way through the consolidation passes. Additional post consolidation passes for the specimens with higher amount of reinforcement layers should be examined in future.

3.3 Bending behaviour

Concerning the flexural behaviour a distribution of maximum stress similarly to the tensile properties could be observed. The specimens that were tested with the reinforcement of the resulting part applicated towards the supports (downside) as well as the specimens with the reinforcement towards the ram of the testing machine (upside) show a significant increase of the averaged maximum stress. It was found that the lay-up of a unidirectional two-ply reinforcement results to an increase of the local flexural strength in a magnitude of 50%. (Fig.5). The lay-up of more than two reinforcements did not result to a further increase of the flexural strength. The comparatively low values concerning the compression loaded specimens (upside) produced with a gas volume of 4Nl/min can be attributed to insufficient polymer healing behaviour and an incomplete melting of the matrix material. The aforementioned behaviour could not be detected within in the specimens reinforced on the downside (tensile load).

3.4 Apparent interlaminar shear strength

All specimens that were reinforced locally with unidirectional tapes with the same kind of matrix type compared to the organic sheet are characterised by high improvements respective to the stress-strain

behaviour. In contrast the matrix inhomogeneous reinforcement decreases the mechanical properties or at least rests at a comparative level to the unreinforced sheets (Fig.6). This behaviour is reflected in the apparent interlaminar shear strength (Fig.7). The matrix homogeneous reinforcement is able to significantly increase the mechanical properties of the resulting hybrid structure in contrast to the inhomogeneous reinforcement. This property is noticeable independent to the matrix type and is caused among other things by the different melting temperatures and the chemical constitution of the two polymers (PA6 & PP).

3.5 Drop weight impact test

Both, the specimens which were matrix homogeneously reinforced by use of thermoplastic in-situ tape placement as well as specimens that were reinforced by press process show increases concerning the puncture resistance (Fig.8). PP-GF organic sheets reinforced with PP-GF tapes through tape placement achieve an average increase of the maximum breaking force of 25.4%. The hybrid structures produced by press process (PP-GF organic sheet / PP-GF reinforcement) show an increase of 20.2 %. In contrast reinforcements with a different matrix type compared to the organic sheets have only the ability to increase the mechanical properties concerning puncture resistance in much lower way. Furthermore not negligible considerations can be determined concerning the different production methods. The samples reinforced by use of in-situ tape placement process show higher impact resistances compared to the press process. As example the impact resistance of the combination PA6-GF organic sheet with PA6-GF reinforcement shows an increase of 17.5 % when using the in-situ tape placement process in contrast to application of the reinforcement via press process (2.5 %). This can be explained by the change in width due to the processing method of the reinforcement. The specimens that were produced by means of press process show an average increase of width by a factor of 2 to 3 (Fig.9+10). Through the press process a significant enlargement of the reinforcing tape is inevitable. This correlates as seen with the mechanical properties. On the contrary the thermoplastic in-situ tape placement process offers the possibility to reinforce the base materials in a much more precise way.

4 Summary

The influence of reinforcements of polymer based thermoplastic organic sheets by in-situ tape placement process was examined. Mechanical improvements concerning tensile and flexural behaviour as well as impact resistance could be detected. A correlation between quantity of reinforcing layers and mechanical properties could be investigated. It could be shown that an increasing number of reinforcement layers needs additional consolidation passes. Compared to the press process a significantly lower expansion of the reinforcement occurs. This could be correlated with the impact resistance. Matrix inhomogeneous reinforcements show less or even no improvements concerning the apparent interlaminar shear strength compared to matrix homogeneous reinforcements.

It could be shown that the thermoplastic in-situ tape placement process can be a competitive process to build-up hybrid structures based on polymer-polymer materials. Compared to the conventional techniques a load-related component design can be manufactured in an optimised manner by the application of local reinforcements using the tape placement method. In future studies, the process will be tested with other material combinations. Before a suitable process setup should be developed for an industrial application a process simulation will be developed and detailed economic aspects have to be analysed.

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Organic sheet	TEPEX dynalite		TEPEX dynalite	
	104-RG600 (4) (OS1)		102-RG600 (4) (OS2)	
	Long.	Trans.	Long.	Trans.
Fibres	roving glass		roving glass	
Fabric	twill 2/2		twill	
Area weight	g/m ² 600		600	
Yarn	tex 1200	1200	1200	1200
Weight rate	% 50	50	50	50
Polymer	PP		PA6	
Density	g/cm ³ 1,69		1,8	
Fibre content	% vol. 47		47	
Thickness per layer	mm 0,5		0,5	
Tensile strength	MPa 415		404	365
Ultimate stress	MPa 365		620	585
Tape	CELSTRAN CFR-TP		CELSTRAN CFR-TP	
	PP-GF70 (T1)		PA6-GF60 (T2)	
Fibres	UD glass		UD glass	
Fibre content	% vol. 45		40	
Matrix	PP		PA6	
Width	mm 12		12	
Thickness	mm 0,25		0,25	
	ACM Plytron			
	GF/PP 35 (T3)			
Fibres	UD glass			
Fibre content	% vol. 35			
Matrix	PP			
Width	mm 12			
Thickness	mm 0,25			
Wedge peel test			(3.1)	
Lay-up	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0)			
Gas volume	Nl/min	4 / 6 / 8 / 10		
Width	mm	15		
Tensile test			(3.2)	
Lay-up	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0)			
	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0/0)			
	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0/0/0)			
	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0/0/0/0)			
Gas volume	Nl/min	4 / 6 / 8 / 10		
Width	mm	25 ± 0,2		
Bending			(3.3)	
Lay-up	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0)			
	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0/0)			
	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0/0/0)			
	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0/0/0/0)			
	° T1 (0), OS1 (0/90/0/90)			
	° T1 (0/0), OS1 (0/90/0/90)			
	° T1 (0/0/0), OS1 (0/90/0/90)			
	° T1 (0/0/0/0), OS1 (0/90/0/90)			
Gas volume	Nl/min	4 / 10		
Width	mm	15 ± 0,2		
Apparent interlaminar shear strength			(3.4)	
Lay-up	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0) / T2 (0)			
	° T1 (0) / T2 (0), OS1 (0/90/0/90)			
	° OS2 (0/90/0/90), T1 (0) / T2 (0)			
	° T1 (0) / T2 (0), OS2 (0/90/0/90)			
Gas volume	Nl/min	6 NL		
Width	mm	15 ± 0,2		
Drop weight impact test			(3.5)	
Lay-up	° OS1 (0/90/0/90), T3 (0/90)			
	° OS2 (0/90/0/90), T3 (0/90)			
Gas volume	Nl/min	4 / 6 / 8 / 10		
T _{press}	°C	OS1 (225), OS2 (270)		
Width	mm	15 ± 0,2		

Table 1: Materials and specimens

Fig.1. Sketch of thermoplastic tape placement process for hybrid structures

Fig.2. Failure behaviour between organic sheet and unidirectional reinforcement (ILSS test)

Fig.3. Averaged peel force

Fig.4. Maximum stress according to reinforcement layers

Fig.5. Bending behaviour according to reinforcement layers and gas volume

Fig. 6. Stress-strain behaviour of reinforced PP-GF organic sheet

Fig. 9. Expansion of PA6-GF reinforcement according to process

Fig. 7. ILSS according to homogeneous/inhomogeneous reinforcement

Fig. 8. Influence of matrix homogeneous and inhomogeneous reinforcement

Fig. 10. Widening of PP-GF reinforcement according to process

References

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